

SHORT NOTES

Occurrence of Liquid Alkaloids in *Vinca Rosea* Linn.

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Since many of the alkaloids, like serpentine, reserpine, akuammine, etc., isolated from *Vinca rosea* Linn., have hypotensive, sedative, tranquillising, and anaesthetic properties^{1,2}, it was considered of interest to undertake a thorough investigation of this plant. Though as many as thirty alkaloids have been isolated from this plant⁴, no reference has been found so far to the presence of a liquid alkaloid in the root-bark of the plant, except a report of an unidentified syrupy alkaloid from the light petroleum extract of the leaves³. Moreover, a survey of the literature of indole alkaloids shows that only two liquid bases of that group have been reported⁵ so far.

For the present work, the root-bark of this species, collected from the shore-side of Trivandrum, has been used. After removal of the strong bases with benzene, the aqueous solution, containing moderately good quantities of alkaloids, was extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract on evaporation provided a dark reddish brown syrupy liquid (0.2%) having a characteristic smell. From this, a pale yellow liquid (Vincaline I) (soluble in water), b.p. 165-67°, and an orange-yellow syrup (Vincaline II) (insoluble in water), b.p. 90-93°/5-6 cm, were separated in small quantities (0.004% & 0.002% respectively) by using the difference in solubility in water. Both of them responded to the usual tests for alkaloids and also colour test with Keller's reagent, which is characteristic of the indole alkaloids. Paper chromatography of these bases provided orange-brown bands with *R_f* values 0.62 and 0.49 and the bands disappeared gradually. Both are moderately weak bases. Because of the highly volatile and unstable nature of the free bases and the difficulty in preparing their salts in a state of sufficient purity, reliable combustion data, molecular weights, and specific rotations of the bases as well as their salts could not be obtained.

Procedure.—The air-dried and powdered root-bark (10 kg.) was successively extracted in a Soxhlet with benzene, acetone, and methanol. The residue from the benzene extract

1. Chopra *et al.*, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1957, 45, 11.
2. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1959, 47, 39.
3. Raymond-Hamet, *Arch. Exptl. Path. Pharmacol.*, 1942, 199, 399.
4. "Physical Data of Indole and Dihydroindole Alkaloids", Lilly Research Laboratories, Indiana, U.S.A., 1956-1963.
5. Aldaba and Belardo, *Rev. Filip. Med. Farm.*, 1937, 28, 308.
6. Manske and Holmes, "The Alkaloids", Vol. II, pp. 469-470,

was treated with cold 3% HCl. The clear aqueous acid solution was defatted with light petroleum, basified, and extracted with benzene till complete isolation of the alkaloid. Thus the alkaloids like ajmalicine, reserpine, serpentine, etc. were removed.

The aqueous layer (2 litres) containing the new alkaloids was extracted with chloroform (1 litre). The chloroform extract after vacuum distillation left a reddish brown syrup (20.8 g.) with a characteristic pungent smell. The syrup was treated with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) at 45°, cooled in a refrigerator, and the clear solution decanted. This was repeated four times until the petroleum extract became colorless and non-alkaloidal. The base was completely extracted from the petroleum solution with HCl (cold, dil.). (The non-alkaloidal petroleum layer on evaporation provided 1.8 g. of a volatile oil, O.I.). The acid solution was basified with NaOH and extracted with peroxide-free ether until the aqueous layer became almost non-alkaloidal. From the ether layer a deep red liquid (5g.) was obtained after distilling the ether. Paper chromatography of this liquid (using *n*-butanol-water-HCl in the ratio of 100:30:4) provided two bands with R_f values 0.49 and 0.62, indicating presence of two alkaloids. This red liquid was shaken with warm distilled water, cooled, and decanted; the operations were repeated till the washings became non-alkaloidal. Thus it was separated into water-soluble and water-insoluble portions.

The water-soluble portion was made acidic with HCl and washed with ether to remove the oily impurities (O.I.). It was next made alkaline with NaOH and extracted with peroxide-free ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and evaporated, when 1.5 g. of an orange liquid was obtained. This was fractionally distilled to provide two fractions: (i) at 81-83° (0.5 g.); (ii) at 165-67° (0.6g., light yellow). The first fraction was a non-alkaloidal oily impurity (O.I.) and the second one was alkaloidal. The second fraction on distillation afforded a light yellow liquid (0.4 g.) at 165-67°. This provided a single orange-brown band on the paper chromatogram, with the R_f value 0.62. This base has been given the name Vincaline I. It is a weak base (pH 8-8.5) with a characteristic pungent smell; it is highly soluble in water and in organic solvents. With Keller's reagent, it showed a dull green ring with blue tinges, changing to bluish green on shaking. The colour faded and disappeared in 30 min. It volatilises at the room temperature, leaving a very little black residue, which is non-alkaloidal. When kept in the dark in air-tight containers, it changes from light yellow liquid to a dark-brown viscous liquid in 8-10 hr. and finally to a dark brown semisolid.

The water-insoluble portion was dissolved in 10% HCl and washed with ether to remove the non-alkaloidal oily impurities (O.I.). Then it was basified with NaOH and extracted with peroxide-free ether. From the ether extract, 0.4g. of a dark brown, syrupy liquid was obtained. This was distilled at a reduced pressure (5-6 cm) and an orange-yellow syrup (0.2 g.) was collected at 90-93°. This provided a single band on the paper chromatogram with the R_f value 0.49. This has been named as Vincaline II. This is insoluble in water and has a pH 9.-9.5. This reacts with the Keller's reagent in an almost similar way as Vincaline I. It changes to a dark brown semisolid in 10-12 hr. at the room temperature.

The same bases could not be obtained from the acetone and methanol extracts of the root-bark. The benzene extract of the fresh juice of root-bark did not also provide the bases.

Salts of Vincaline I

Hydrochloride.—To the liquid base (104 mg.), dissolved in dry ether, was added dry ethereal HCl. A dull white precipitate formed changed to a black sticky mass (108 mg.) in a few seconds. The odourless salt regained the characteristic smell of the free base when treated with NaOH. The same was found even after keeping the hydrochloride for a long time and converting it into the free base. No loss in weight of the salt was found even after a few days. So this suggests that the salt is more stable than the free base. It could neither be crystallised nor obtained in the form of an amorphous powder.

Picrate.—The base (70 mg.) was dissolved in absolute methanol (5 ml). To a portion of this solution (1.8 ml) was added a methanolic solution (0.8 ml) of picric acid (1 ml containing 21 mg. of the acid) and warmed. This was evaporated and dried in a desiccator to a constant weight (44 mg.). It could not be crystallised; m.p. 180-86° (decomp.).

Reineckate.—An aqueous solution (1 ml) of the base (17 mg.) was acidified with HCl (dil.) and to this was added ammonium reineckate solution (4 ml containing 100 mg. of the salt). The dark brown precipitate formed was filtered and dried (28 mg.). It is non-crystallisable; m.p. 236-39° (decomp.).

The oily impurities (referred as O.I.), obtained at different stages of the isolation of the above bases, were identified as one and the same. This volatile oil has a penetrating smell; b.p. 82-84°, d_{20}^{20} 0.9824. It formed a crystalline red 2,4 DNP; m.p. 181-83°. The oil does not show any reducing action and hence it may contain a keto group.

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